

Jordan In Counterterrorism, Threats, and Strategy

Mohammed B. E. Saaida

AL-Istiqlal University

Abstract:

This Research paper tries to bring to the causes of the current terrorist threats in Jordan in the chaotic region and the methods of combating terrorism. It focuses on mainly on the Jordanian policy and strategy for combating terrorism including legal, diplomatic, and security efforts. The impact of the Syrian crisis on this poor resources country causing undeniable political, economic, social and security threats. The article shows the efforts of Jordan to fight terrorism through national and international strategy by joining the International Alliance against ISIS. Jordan holds a significant role in this battle on multi-dimensions.

Introduction:

Jordan faces great challenges in terms of stability in a region wrecked with a seemingly unending conflict and political chaos. After the so-called Arab Spring, one of the reasons that has emerged and added which increased the growing threatening dangers of terrorism. With the rise of Islamic State in Iraq and Syria (ISIS) that occupied a large span of land in Syria and Iraq, which has become a kind of a magnet for terrorists all over the world. This consequently becomes a threat to the whole region and especially to vulnerable states like Jordan. Jordan has its own history of terrorist attacks that led the policy makers in the country to reconsider the motivations and

causes of such attacks in order to come up with vital decisions that ensure lowest cost and loss. In response to the rise of ISIS, Jordan has decided to make fighting terrorism its top priority, culminated in 2015, through adapting a counterterrorism strategy so that the country can stay unscathed by the effects of the destabilized neighboring regions, which are already yoked under terrorist activities. This adapted strategy is still active.

Being one of the major Western Allies, Jordan's stability in West Asia is doubtlessly very essential to the stability of the whole region. The country is not only a major partner in combating ISIS, but also playing a constructive role in supporting the peace process of the Palestinian-Israeli conflict. Since Jordan has its cooperation with its treaty partner, Israel, national instability or chaos in Jordan might threaten the established status quo and this might result in unwanted consequences such as putting the treaties with Israel and the U.S. at stake.

The growth of population caused by the Syrian refugees in Jordan correspondingly necessities for implementing some measures of austerity. These measures in fact could provoke destabilizing and anti-regime emotion in the country. Although Islamic State stimulating terrorist attacks in Jordan would likely produce a rally-around-the-flag effect, such issues along with other security issues could further damage the Jordanian economy, that is already fragile, and thereby resulting in instability, causing a crisis, possibly because of nagging voices among the refugee population and dissatisfied Jordanians alike.

The Islamic State's existence in the West Asia has overwhelming consequences which go beyond the West Asian region. The ongoing conflict in West Asia and North Africa and the increasing state of confusion create an urgent demand for interference, to prevent the Islamic State's

expansion. In order to do so, Jordan has developed an innovative and significant strategy and campaigns along with efforts of the security forces.

One has to mention here that terrorism is not a new phenomenon. It had been existed for a long time but never been more as notorious as it have become towards the end of Cold War in the last quarter of the 20th century until now. Causes may go to the decrease of the world as a result of globalization and information technology revolution.

Jordan in the Middle of a Troubled Region

Needless to say, West Asia is in turmoil. All countries are not immune to the threat of terrorism. If one is to compare it to its neighbors, Jordan has very limited terrorist attacks in the recent years. Among the major current political conflicts in West Asia is the old-and-new unresolved Palestinian-Israeli conflict, the Iraqi war against ISIS, the manufactured Sunni-Shia conflict, Egyptian crisis in Sinai, the Yemeni Crisis, the Syrian crisis, the Libyan crisis, combating terrorism and the recent Gulf crisis. In addition to this is the economic problems due to the stumbled developments, largely because of destabilization of the region due to interventions done by international and regional powers in several areas.

As far as the Israeli-Palestinian conflict, the Israeli aggression against the Palestinian still persists and Israel is still increasing its settlements, violating the international law, making no space for peace. Egypt, which is facing increasing economic crisis and thereby coming to a political deadlock, is fighting terrorism in Sinai. The Kingdom of Saudi Arabia along with its allies is

struggling to contain the Houthis in the southern part of Yemen. At the same time, terrorist groups are fighting to gain more land and strengthen their abilities in Syria and Iraq.

Similar to other countries, Jordan is witnessing the rise of fundamentalism, which is a major reason for the international terrorism spread. These movements rejected the modern secular societies that thrive to separate religion from politics. Whatever the politicians or the pundits claim, people all over the world are demonstrating and demanding to see religion reflected more prominently in public life. As part of their campaign, fundamentalists tend to withdraw from mainstream society to create enclaves of pure faith.

The world in general and West Asia, in particular, witnessed the rise of religious fundamentalism through the terrorist actions done by the religions' followers whether it is Islam, Judaism, Christianity, Hinduism or Buddhism. Suicide bombing and genocide massacre are done by name of religion. The fundamentalist groups share the same categories; faith and salvation (Rogers, et al. 2007).

Religious terrorism, which is executed by those whose inspirations and aims have an overwhelming religious impact, is based on the confusion of theological epithets, or it could be the consequence of outrageous types of delusion that may change reality, and subsequently subject an individual or a group of people to mutilated forms of religious certainties and episodes like 'just war theory', liberation theology, Inquisitions and the Crusades. Religious terrorism consists of acts that terrify; the definition of which is provided by the witnesses the ones terrified and not by the party committing the act; joined by a religious motivation, justification, organization, or world view (Odhiambo, 2014). One has to mention here that till date there is no consensus on the definition as the UN has failed to provide one.

The scientific advancement of information technologies is tremendously facilitating the expansion of terrorism to an international level. This makes the scientific development as a double edge weapon. On the one hand, it can be used as a means of spreading ideas and thoughts through countless free and easy communication applications. On the other hand, it simultaneously can be used for fighting terrorism itself.

Jordan had been attacked severely in 2005 by bombings at hotels in Amman. Al-Qaeda in Iraq declared its responsibility for the attacks which caused 60 death. Spurred to take action, the Jordanian authorities took certain security measures that increased all around the country thereby threats were rapidly recognized and eradicated. In subsequent years after this devastating event, the Kingdom had been affected by minor cases as the assaults committed remained partial, causing few victims. Ten years later, Jordan's terrorism combating security ability has advanced progress and enhanced markedly. (Terrorism in Jordan – A growing risk? 2017)

ISIS, which was created in Iraq and then moved towards Syria made a major change in West Asia. The weakness of the Syrian and Iraqi governments, due the destabilization, created an excellent environment for such political body to flourish. ISIS is guided by the idealized image of the Islamic history of Islamic Caliphate ruling the Muslim World in place of modern states which work in favor of the Western States' interests. Jordan realized the current objectives of ISIS which is at its core harkening to a wider conflict between the Sunni in contrast to the flourishing Shi'ite power led by Tehran. The ever-changing politics in West Asia affected also by important changes in super power stance to the whole region. (Rabi, 2015)

Clearly, Jordan is in the agenda of ISIS as through eliminating all borders after seizing more land since ISIS declared its Islamic Caliphate. Since the Islamist movements in Jordan has a

significant influence and presence, and due to the long shared borders of Jordan with Iraq and Syria, this encourages ISIS to make efforts to infiltrate the Kingdom (LaMarca, 2014).

Indeed, the Arab Spring helped in the rise of ISIS. There is a longstanding and extensively known opposite connection between self-governing societies and violence. The further that democracy spread in the right practice of political responsibility, community transparency and the nonviolent transmission of authority, the fewer the probability of violence is founded (Hashemi, 2016).

The Terrorism Impacts of Syrian Crisis on Jordan:

Jordan is one of the main countries that had been affected directly by the consequences of the Syrian Crisis. The ongoing crisis has started in 2011. In the past, Jordan was sharply hit by the Palestinian (1947, 1967) and the Iraqi (1991, 2003) crises. In reaction, the Jordanian foreign policy was guided by the high interests of the Jordanian state in that time. The formal positions reflected the Jordanian attitudes and policies towards each issue locally, regionally and internationally.

As actions took place in Syria, Jordan took a neutral side and tried to remain diplomatic, and distance itself as much as possible of what is going on in Syria considering it an internal affair of Syria that it should not interfere with it. Jordan did not evict the Syrian ambassador till the year 2014, unlike other Arab countries that did so, despite the indirect threats every now and then to expand and move the conflict to the Jordanian territories.

After six years and by the end of the year 2016 more than 4.5 million Syrian refugees crossed the borders leaving for the neighboring countries. The majority fled to Jordan, Turkey, Iraq and

Lebanon. Jordan hosted more than 600 thousand refugees due to U.N. Statistics (Jordan Government and UNDP, 2015)

The major impacts that affected Jordan were the influx of Syrian refugees and the rise of terrorism. Jordan received Syrian refugees since the beginning of the Syrian crisis which reached over 600 thousand refugees seeking asylum till 2016. The rise of terrorism is the second result of the Syrian crisis. The international alliance in the Middle East plays a vital role between the regional countries and superpowers where the status of chaos exists next to the borders of any country neighboring to stable countries there. The Syrian crisis resulted three main terroristic threats on Jordan:

- 1. Islamic Terrorist Groups Threats to Jordan:** The chaos caused by the Syrian crisis helped in the rise and strengthening of fundamental terrorism that is resembled by The Islamic State in Sham and Iraq (ISIS). Jordan suffered from the threats of ISIS. Violence actions had been practiced in Jordan by ISIS. This threat is totally against the Jordanian high interest to keep the Jordanian society stabled.

Counterterrorism is a new case for the Jordanian military agencies. The detentions of ISIS supporters by Jordanian security emphasize shows how Jordan acts seriously against the threats of extremism and terrorism. The government puts great efforts in campaigns to promote the moderation and tolerance of Islam against the extremist's radical ideologies in the minds of the ISIS and Al Qaeda affiliates, (Abbadi, 2015).

- 2. Terrorists among the Syrian refugees' Influx:** Jordan fears of hiding terrorist among the refugees. The terrorists flow is a big challenge to the Jordanian security agencies. They have great opportunity to stay away from the eyes of security. This situation forces

Jordan to take some important procedures in order to avoid being hit again (Malkawi, 2015).

Over the past six years, Jordan received over 600 thousand refugees seeking asylum pushed by the violence in Syria. Five camps for refugees were opened such as Za'atari, Azraq, Marjeeb Al Fhood, Rukban, and Hadallat. Some of the refugees can move from one location to another or to isolated remote areas in Jordan. It is believed that the refugees' crisis had created bad impacts on the Jordanian economy, social and security dimensions. Jordan with short economic and natural resources under critical pressure is trying to host the refugees the thing that creates another threat to Jordan (Jordan Government and UNDP, 2013).

- 3. Jordanian fighters join the terrorists groups:** Since the beginning of the Syrian Crisis in 2011, it is estimated that more than 30,000 foreign fighters had joined the terroristic groups, such as al-Qaeda and ISIS, in Iraq and Syria. It is estimated that three thousand Jordanian fighters joined them. The fighters are pushed by frustrations with governance, unemployment, unequal opportunities and the spread of militant jihadi beliefs. Jordan is an active supplier of outsider fighters to the neighboring Iraq and Syria. Al Zarqawi Jihadist give a clear example of what could happen from a regular citizen. The violent extremists have succeeded to awake of Jihadists inside Jordan to motivate and launch attacks inside Jordan. Regardless of whether Jordanian fighters stay or go home, still they create a threat to the Kingdom (Speckhard, 2017).

Jordan under Big Threats of ISIS:

The situation in West Asia has become more complicated by the expansion of the Islamic State in Iraq and Syria and Egypt and Libya. Such undeniable heavyweight terrorist group supported by an army forms a real risk for Jordan the neighbor of Iraq and Syria and close enough to Egypt. The power of ISIS cannot be underestimated. This had been proven clearly in Mosul when the whole city fall into their hands in 2014 with a blink of an eye. It became closer to the northern borders of Jordan. There are other terrorist organizations; Al-Nusra Front, Afnad al-Sham, Khalid Ibn Al-Walid Army, Nour al-Din al-Zenki Movement, Tawhid Army, Muhajirin wal-Ansar Alliance, Jund al-Aqsa and other organizations and groups (Souriat E-Newspaper, 2015)

For Jordan, being at the edge of the cliff is not a comfortable matter. The Jordanian society is conservative. It had some tendency toward the Islamism. It is not a secret that three thousands of Jordanians who went to fight in Syria had joined ISIS. The Islamic Parties in Jordan are active in the Jordanian streets. The Islamic Action Front (Muslims Brothers Islamic party) is the most active. These Islamic parties are not following the Salafists thoughts and yet the majority of the Jordanian society members considered ISIS and Al Qaeda terrorist groups.

It is not a secret that Jordan is within the strategic goals of ISIS. The Islamic States propaganda published a primary imagined map of the future State of Islamic Khilafah then to include later the whole world getting out of Iraq and Syria then Jordan and Kuwait..etc. reaching Palestine. The Islamic State managed to challenge the transponder of the states that had been but in Sykes–Picot colonial Agreement. That encouraged it to expand the appetite of nationalism and activating the religious duties to reshape the Islamic Empire (Jordan under the shadow of Salafism, (2016)

During the last three years, there were noticed wide geographic and demographic developments in the Jordanian jihadists' activities. The numbers of Jihadists reached over 7000 Jihadist in addition to the supporters. The distribution is in all cities and governorates and found in all of the society's classes. But, they are focused in high density in specific cities like Zarqa and Rusayfeh where the population is high. They are found in many other poor areas in Amman, Salt city, Ma'an city and in the Palestinian refugees' camps. These poor areas are characterized by great feelings of being marginalized the thing that caused a sense of deprivation and poverty and unfair. The jihadists are derived from both Jordanian and Palestinian families. This means a start of a new incubator of terrorism, especially in Zarqa and Ma'an. The reproduction laboratories of jihadists in Jordan became ready to work, just they need time and orders (Schenker, 2014).

The burning of the Jordanian pilot by ISIS in 2015 provoked common anger and hatred against the Islamic State in Jordan, and belief by leading persons of the Islamic world and consequently led the government of Jordan to execute ISIS members which previously judged by death sentences on 2005 Bombs attack in Amman.

Recently, Jordan became a target of several terror attacks. The newest attack happened on December 18, 2016, when a group of four Jordanian nationals struck a number of targets in Karak city south of Jordan. The fight resulted four security men were killed, with other civilians and one Canadian tourist. The Islamic State (ISIS) declared responsibility for the incident. Later on, investigations revealed that the attackers were in prison for time for attempting to join (ISIS) (Bremmer, 2017).

The increasing number of deadly attacks carried out by ISIS members from Jordanian nationality, along with the worrying numbers of Jordanians jumping into the laps of the Salafi-jihadi groups existing in Iraq and Syria, have triggered big concern in the kingdom (Harel, 2017).

Another reason helped and pushed the common opinion in Jordanian society to see ISIS as an enemy. The governmental campaigns in media against terrorism were served a lot by the pilot's killing. A big wave of shock created the feelings of horror among the Jordanians. The citizens touched the real danger of ISIS (Abu Rmoan, Samer, 2015)

While incident occurrence in Jordan still low, there are reasons to believe that terrorists are present in the Jordan and are looking to conduct more attacks. ISIS members in the Kingdom have issued dangers to target the King Abdullah II regime; hundreds of fighters who have deep roots in Jordan who have traveled to fight for ISIS and other militants may return, whether as part of an ISIS plan or in reaction to big losses in Syria and Iraq. In addition, as many assaults in Europe have proved, there is danger from lonely self-radicalized individuals who are fascinated by the ideology of ISIS to make attacks in their countries. These could be normal citizens or even an armed forces members with access to extraneous military or inhabitant personnel. Indeed, ISIS has specifically encouraged lone wolfs violence via its several propaganda platforms. The Jordanian security agencies remain alerted to the danger and carry a high ability to encounter the challenges; but, as the 18 December Karak city incident and other incidents through 2016 shown, they the security agencies cannot entirely eradicate the threat or to stay prevented from attacks.

ISIS attacks methods regionally have contained lone attackers and another type which is the multiple militants deployed against both hard and soft targets. Given the highest security in

Jordan, public casualty and complex assaults, including gun and bomb attacks, are most of them near the borders with Iraq and Syria than the main urban areas inside Jordan. There is a noticed security and political vacuum in western Iraq and southern Syria, which enables ISIS variety of movement and operation. In Jordan, attacks are focused on soft targets and executed by small number groups of singular suicide bombers or gunmen. Patrols, checkpoints, and weak secured state institutions are likely the easy targets. Western interests, including businesses and diplomatic facilities, the prime targets of areas where Westerners gather, such as hotels, restaurants and tourist areas. The problem is that the unknown time and place for any attack requires a rapid deployment of trained forces of counter terrorism (Susser, 2015)

The sense of danger of ISIS was increased by the existence of Islamic Militants which follows ISIS in south Syria at the Jordanian-Syrian borders in addition to the attacks' series that happened in Jordan by ISIS and Al Qaeda. Jordan believes that it will not be a backyard of the Syrian fighting parties, especially for the terrorist groups who flee from the war in Syrian. The belief in the peaceful solutions (Al-Monitor, 2017)

Terrorism affects the Jordanian national security as happened in the other countries, terrorism tries to achieve its political objectives by terror. Therefore, Terrorism led by ISIS is a clear violation of human rights of locals, international law and legal norms on the one hand, and traditions and religious norms. It is a new situation in the Jordanian society. It is leading to horror, fear, and panic among the public or a group of particular people and sometimes it makes no difference who is targeted. This poses a threat to international peace and countries security and societies and exposes the internal and international stability and friendly relations between

nations. The terrorist groups became a weapon used by some countries as an alternative to conventional wars in its struggle and its pursuit of its strategic interests and objectives, regardless of the legitimacy of the means leading to it and sometimes resorting to direct and indirect terrorist acts to achieve its objectives (Mohammad, 2011).

International terrorism appears to be a fundamental indicator of the violation and taking off many of the original human rights guaranteed by religions, conventions, and charters through international human rights law. Jordan joined the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights in 1948, as well as the Covenants on Civil and Political Rights (Mohammad, 2011).

Jordan does not want to go in the case of terrorism like what is happening in Syria, Iraq, and Libya. The civilians are easy targets for all kinds of attacks and weapons. Fear and panic are everywhere. The states there became unsafe countries. The destruction might occur in various forms causing a destruction of homes and burning property and the causing of material losses. Yemen is another good example for the insecure state. The Yemeni government is unable to secure its citizens, borders, and economy. Syria, Iraq, Libya, and Yemen seem to be the terrorism land. Refugees fled away to Jordan and the neighboring countries. The Jordanian authorities recognize that some of them might hold the seeds of terrorism with them.

Terroristic actions has direct and indirect effects on security of Jordan's economy. It is noted that as the government spends much on the security in the country, businesses have become vulnerable to probable terrorist targets, with important implications for the foreign investments or performance of multinational firms. Any probable terrorist incidents if affects sensitive economy elements and business in Jordan, the petrol refinery, for example, would cost great loss and creates chaos among people. Terror incidents also occur in Jordan just like other countries

globally leading to significant socioeconomic consequences. The terror actions and violence will create an insecure environment for economic investment in any country (Aly, A. M. S., & Feldman, S. 2015).

The Jordanian Strategy against Terrorism

The Jordanian authorities recognized that Jordan is not far away from the dangers that the Islamic State forms. The increasing sounds of war drums coming from of ISIS toward Jordan stimulated the Kingdom to respond and react in the proper way it sees before it is too late. The Salafist groups' members still support ISIS and other similar terrorists the thing that make the situations worst. The declaration of ISIS of establishing base in Jordan in order to start providing it with logistic made the Kingdom take preventive measures to face the threats through deployment of the Jordanian troops on the borders with Syria and Iraq with more forces in addition to enforcement of internal policies, laws, regulations, and measures to have more discipline which leads to detaining the terrorist supporters (Schenker, 2014)

There are three major motivations which encourage ISIS to look eagerly to Jordan:

First: the Jordanian contribution with the international coalition against ISIS. Jordan is a strategic ally to with the United States in its war against terrorism and the regional threats. This had been shown through providing the logistic and intelligence services to the international coalition. Also, Jordan opened the Jordanian air space to launch for the international coalition fighting aircraft and drones to do airstrikes on ISIS locations. The Jordanian Salafist extremist opposed that and condemned it.

Second: the geographic expansion of ISIS in Jordan would strongly provide the Islamic State with vital crossing point to be enhanced. ISIS captures area is Iraq 60 kilometers away from Jordan and closer to the borders. Jordan's land can be used also to reach Sinai in Egypt, as Abu Bakr Al Baghdadi the ISIS leader sees.

Third: The thoughts' expansion through the supporters in Jordan. This expansion of jihadist and religious thoughts facilitate moving into neighbors' land easily. Demonstrations went out in streets in Ma'an south of Jordan calling for Jihad. Many of the Salafi jihadists in Jordan were in the battle fields in Afghanistan, Iraq, and Syria (Schenker, 2014).

Jordan's move to the threats is building a comprehensive strategy to combat terrorism depends on five elements:

1. Legal modifications in the Anti-Terrorism Law: the parliament of Jordan ratified the legal modifications in the Anti-Terrorism Law in 2014. The government and the security agencies were given wide authorities. New concepts of terrorism issue were added or modified. The Muslim Brothers and the Human right organizations criticized this move as it was followed by wide detention campaign for whom showed sympathy in public with ISIS resulting detention of 300 persons. Meanwhile, 25 Imams were prohibited from preaching in mosques for violating the law and promoting for intellectual and religious extremism.
2. High ministerial committee for facing terrorism: this committee were formed recently as result of the increasing Salafist movements in cities and villages of Jordan. The goal of the committee is to face the hardliners politically, socially intellectually and with security

means also, if necessary. The representatives of the committee are found all over the Jordanian establishments to observe the extremists closely.

3. The deployment of Jordanian troops across the border with Iraq and Syria. The deployment came after the controlling of ISIS the lands on shared borders of Syria and Iraq with Jordan. The United States supported Jordan with military assistance. During 2016, Jordan kept on strengthening its long border with Iraq and Syria to reduce its proximity danger, specifically, to stop access by terrorists and to control large influx of refugees. In June 2016, a possible infiltrating men were killed when an ISIS suicide man explode along the Jordan-Syria border at Rukba refugees camp, killing six Jordanian security men. Later on, Jordan's counter terrorism services have recognized and stopped several threats. In March 2016, security attack at a refugee camp of Palestinian in the north is Jordan caused seven assumed ISIS men dead. Officials showed that the suspects were preparing attacks in the kingdom. Other important progress in the year was the June 2016 killing of five state personnel in the Palestinian Baqaa refugee camp near the capital Amman and the November 2016 killing of three US security members in al-Jafr at the King Faisal Air Base. Both incidents, committed by lone gunmen, were measured at the period as dropping within the baseline risk assessment of medium. The two incidents were followed by a big attack on 18 December 2016 in Karak.
4. Joining the international coalition against terrorism with other 62 countries. Jordan military bases contain the operations room for collecting analyzing and exchanging data and coordination the action in addition to observations (Drennan, 2014).

5. The Jordanian government launched campaigns to promote tolerance thoughts of Islam instead of extremist thoughts. Promoting to follow the peaceful ways in progressive debate and expressing thoughts. The campaigns are fulfilled by the official social society establishment, media, schools, universities and social media space (Altarawneh, 2016)

Conclusion

Terrorism is a global phenomenon, coming out of an extreme ideology and experienced by most of the nations. The Jordan is suffering as a bitter result of this threatening phenomenon. Terrorism is used to achieve political goals by groups who follow unacceptable thoughts against humanity. Unfortunately, the targets of violence are innocent people who just want to live a peaceful life. The danger of terrorists' actions leads to committing horrible crimes by killing innocent people, destroying property and damaging social infrastructure and influencing the world in a very negative way.

Jordan, which is suffering from ISIS terrorist attacks, has played a significant role in the combat against extremism now in many different and multiple fronts. Jordan has adopted a clear and stable policy based on an information system network and developed strong relations with other countries fighting terrorism in order to cooperate and exchange security information at the international and regional level. This approach allows the Jordan along with other countries be effective in tackling terrorist threats. It had shown Jordan's partners the credibility of Jordan to

fight terrorist groups in their territories the matter that led to a notable increase in achieving and enhancing the Jordanian citizen's stability and security.

Jordan focuses on its strategy on Islam as a religion of faith and tolerance, equality, justice, and mercy. Islam has no any relation with terrorism and believed that terrorism does not belong to religions or lands or races. Jordan, its citizens, officials, and interests have been a targeted by terrorism because of its righteous principled position and its effort in rejecting and fighting all forms of extremism. The Jordanian leadership determined to continue to combat terrorism and its committees with all possible and available means. Stability and security are Jordan's top priority and no tolerance with the terrorist organization or individual from all origins. Jordan considers that resorting to security and military means will not be enough sufficient to uproot international and regional terrorism. In order to fully eliminate terrorism sufficiently, the government is putting the economic and social factors into consideration in addition to other root reasons for this phenomenon. The government in Jordan counts on the Jordanian people to stand with it in its battle. The Jordanian Jihadists are in the strategic plan. Still, they have to chance to change their attitudes and commit no prohibited actions violating the Anti-Terrorism law.

As for the Syrian refugees, Jordan announced that in spite of the shortage of natural resources it is Jordan's duty to provide the refugees with the suitable and proper shelter and asylums. This stance comes out of the neighborhood ties with Syria and from Islam values and the call of humanity along with the international humanitarian law regarding the refugees in war time and other international conventions on human rights.

Jordan declared that it is an essential integral part of the international coalition to combat terrorism without any intervention in the conflict over authority in Syria. Jordan has regularly

expressed its condemnation and sincere sorrow of all forms and practices of terrorism and stands steadily ready to coordinate and cooperate with the international community to fight this phenomenon. The belief of the Jordanian leadership is that terrorist practices go in contrast with the religious and human values of civilized human. Additionally, Amman loses no opportunities to underline the importance of fighting terrorism everywhere without of any double standards practices.

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